

Ideational Dynamics in BRICS+: Why Member States' Values Matter

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Abstract

This paper examines the evolving capacity of the BRICS grouping to function as a site of policy-making. Originally conceived as a loose coalition of emerging economies, the bloc has gradually developed institutional mechanisms and cooperative agendas that extend beyond the economic sphere. Drawing on institutionalist literature - particularly Campbell's framework on institutional change and Schmidt's discursive institutionalism - the paper argues that understanding BRICS+ as an emerging "geopolitical coalition", as Garcia (2025) puts it, requires close attention to the ideational and political dynamics that underpin its institutional development. This process is complicated by the bloc's consensus-based decision-making model facing a growing ideological diversity among its members, particularly following the 2024 expansion. Domestic political shifts within member states can significantly alter the commitment to BRICS initiatives, generating periods of institutional strain. The bloc's future capacity to move beyond symbolic cooperation will depend on its ability to reconcile internal ideological differences while maintaining consensus within an increasingly heterogeneous membership.

Keywords: BRICS+; Intra-BRICS Dynamics; Ideational Dynamics; Institutional

Introduction

The BRICS grouping stemmed from a term coined by economist Jim O'Neill in 2001 to describe the economic rise of Brazil, Russia, India, and China. What began as a financial acronym soon evolved into a diplomatic platform - a cooperation forum between the governments of its member states - with the first BRIC summit in 2009 and South Africa joining in 2010. Over the following decade, the bloc gradually expanded its agenda beyond economic coordination, developing institutional mechanisms such as the New Development Bank and a growing number of sectoral cooperation forums.

The growing scope of its cooperative mechanisms intensified debates about its role in global governance and its capacity to function as a diplomatic forum and more. This gradual institutionalization culminated in the 2024 expansion of the bloc - now "BRICS+" - which significantly increased its geopolitical visibility and internal diversity. Accounting for that, this paper adopts a "sideways" intra-BRICS analytical framework, proposed by Garcia (2025), highlighting its internal dynamics, including processes of institutional and thematic densification and political heterogeneity among member states.

Despite a growing relevance of intra-BRICS political interactions, much of the literature on the grouping has tended to interpret it primarily through the lenses of purely economic cooperation and strategic reform of (or balancing against) Western-led institutions. While these approaches bring important insights, they often overlook the role that ideas, values, and political discourse within BRICS+ countries play in shaping how cooperation within the bloc develops and how collective agendas are articulated.

This paper argues that understanding the institutional evolution of BRICS+ requires taking ideational dynamics of its member states seriously. Drawing on institutionalist rhetoric, particularly the frameworks of John L. Campbell's on institutional change and Vivien A. Schmidt's on discursive institutionalism, the proposal is that BRICS is better analyzed when thought of as an arena where political actors continuously negotiate norms and priorities that guide collective action. This perspective highlights how the values and political orientations of member states influence the development of cooperative agendas and institutional practices.

Therefore a conceptual argument is advanced: the evolving capacity of BRICS+ to function as a site of policy-making is deeply shaped by the ideational interactions among its members and their representatives. Moments of political tension due to global crisis illustrate how internal ideological dynamics can affect the bloc's cohesion and policy trajectory. By foregrounding these dynamics, the paper contributes to ongoing debates about the nature of BRICS as an emerging geopolitical coalition and highlights the importance of ideational factors in understanding its institutional development.

Understanding the BRICS+ Capability For Policy-Making

In recent years, the BRICS grouping has evolved beyond its original characterization as a "loose coalition of emerging economies" (Garcia, 2025). The expansion of the bloc and the gradual development of institutional mechanisms beyond the mere economic dimension have increasingly positioned it as a visible actor in global governance. This transformation raises an important analytical question: to what extent can BRICS be understood not merely as a loose grouping, but as an institutional space capable of producing policy and shaping collective political action? Addressing this question requires examining that there are institutional dynamics promoting coordination and cooperation within the bloc, as well as mechanisms through which its members articulate shared agendas.

To start, one can look at the most recent BRICS+ agenda, set for 2025 with Brazil at the helm, which builds the bloc's image and collective identity around cooperation in non-economic fields. Amongst its pillars for "Politics and Security", "Economy and Finance" and "People-to-People" (P2P) cooperation, it included Work Groups dedicated to themes such as "non-western strategies for education" (BRICS Brasil, 2025c), and contemporary priorities of the bloc notably include efforts in scientific and health cooperation, with the Global Alliance for the Elimination of Socially Determined Diseases and the BRICS Vaccine Research and Development Center (BRICS Brasil, 2025b).

Garcia (2025) points this process as one of "thematic densification", wherein the group's scope has expanded beyond the New Development Bank (NDB), making security and political issues no longer secondary to economic ones. In that sense, she nominates the bloc's current moment as a movement towards becoming a "geopolitical coalition". Following that understanding, we could, then, suggest and argue that the process of policy-making is a growing preoccupation inside of BRICS+ mechanisms.

As proposed by Campbell (2004), policy-making is fundamentally a process of developing or changing institutions; whether those be the formal type (regulations, laws and rules) or the more "informal procedures and practices that eventually become so taken-for-granted as to be assumed appropriate and legitimate" (Campbell, 2004, p.92). In this sense, the aforementioned efforts to diversify operations beyond the economic field serve as dimensions where new systems of meaning are constructed. This process suggests that BRICS members are engaged in exchanges where the values and principles that prescribe behavior are being subtly realigned through constant interaction and learning. In Campbell's (2004) framework, we can call this "institution building".

To understand how this transition from an economic acronym to a "geopolitical coalition" is possible, we must look at what Schmidt (2010) calls the "ideational abilities" of the actors involved. She posits that, within the framework of discursive institutionalism, sentient agents

possess two distinct capacities: background ideational abilities, which allow them to maintain and make sense of existing institutional rules, and foreground discursive abilities. The latter represent the agents' capacity to "think outside the institutions" in which they act and to communicate critically about them to promote change (Schmidt, 2010, p.22). By mobilizing their foreground discursive abilities, BRICS representatives thus act as "sentient agents": reflexive actors capable of deliberating on and stating new intentions (Schmidt, 2010). This interactive process is what allows the bloc to overcome entrenched interests and use persuasive discourse to build the coalitions necessary to challenge the status quo of the Western-led international order.

This dimension reveals, then, that the process of policy-making within BRICS+ is highly vulnerable to the "sentient agents" internal ideological shifts. Not only is the bloc composed of states with markedly different domestic political orientations, but it is still heavily dependent on the importance given to its agenda by each government in power inside of its member states. The far-right turn in Brazil's leadership under Jair Bolsonaro (2019 - 2022), for example, proved detrimental to many BRICS initiatives, bringing forth a period of institutional strain where the "common sense" of South-South cooperation was nearly supplanted by an alignment with Northern-led protectionist agendas (Garcia, 2025).

This institutional fragility is further complicated by the expanded membership of BRICS+, made official in 2024, which wrestles even more political and ideological inconsistencies with the admission of several diverse states (including rivals such as Iran and Saudi Arabia). With that move, the grouping had a deeply political decision be made without clearly defined technical or objective criteria for admitting the new members (Garcia, 2025). Still operating under a consensus-based decision-making model, the bloc must now reconcile these internal imbroglios while simultaneously defending itself and its image against Northern-led governance norms.

Preoccupations with the potential for internal paralysis following the 2024 expansion does not come merely from a speculative or theoretical place: its roots can be traced back to institutional strains like the one faced following the 2014 Russian invasion of Crimea and especially the full scale war with Ukraine in 2022. Ever since the international sanctions put in place against the Kremlin in response, the unit capacity of the bloc has been tested as Russia utilized its membership to counteract international isolation and signal that Western-led sanctions would not be enough to enforce Western global hegemony (Ramos et al., 2018). The diverse reactions of member states during this crisis, thus, reveal a susceptibility to political imbroglios that seems to be inherent in a consensus-based model lacking ideological coordination or standardized entry criteria.

All of these considerations indicate that to overlook the political-ideological dimension of the BRICS is to lose sight of the primary force currently shaping its trajectory. Thus, it becomes vital to stay attentive to the underlying values behind the movements which sediment the BRICS+' "thematic densification", seen as the survival of the institution rests on

its ability to maintain consensus amidst the diverse and sometimes volatile political shifts of its constituent states. This densification is not a settled bureaucratic reality, but a perpetual normative contest.

Defending The Importance of Observing Values Within BRICS

In a bloc where decisions are made by consensus and membership criteria remain loosely defined, the interaction among member states is one between actors who possess the ideational capacities to both sustain and transform institutions. In this sense, BRICS forums increasingly function as arenas where competing geopolitical priorities are negotiated and translated into collective initiatives. Therefore, assessing whether and how the bloc engages in policy-making becomes essential for understanding its role in contemporary global governance. As suggested in the previous section, such engagement has its pillars in the values and principles that prescribe behavior to the sentient agents.

This engagement is also best understood through the second of Garcia's (2025) dimension analysis of the grouping, which focuses on intra-BRICS dynamics. Her framework as whole proposes the following dimensions of analysis: (a) Top-Down or Geopolitical and Interstate Dispute, which views BRICS through the lens of the international system and the power struggle between states, (b) Sideways or Intra-BRICS Dynamics and Asymmetries, which will be further explored in this study, and (c) Bottom-Up or Relations with the Global South and Civil Society, which explores BRICS countries as regional powers and the role of non-state actors. The sideways approach is emphasized here because it focuses on the internal relationship between members, examining their "convergences and disputes" (Garcia, 2025, p. 07) while considering the significant asymmetries (economic and political) that characterize them.

The political outcomes inside of BRICS+, then, can be understood as dependent "not only on the power positions of institutional actors, but also largely on how they, based on their beliefs, interpret and perceive their interests" (Perissinotto and Stumm, 2017, p.128). Member states possess what these authors call "ideational idiosyncrasies" that, due to the historical and contextual nature of beliefs, lead to possibly vastly different behaviors even if actors are placed in situations and institutions similar in their morphological design. In the context of BRICS+, we can observe for instance that while Russia utilizes the bloc to promote a "post-Western civilizational ideology" to subvert the current order, other members like Brazil or India may interpret their interests through a "reformist" lens, seeking a place at the table rather than a radical break (Tsygankov & Muhwezi, 2025, p.2).

Within this dimension, it serves us well to remember Garcia's (2025) analysis of a "thematic densification" within BRICS+, creating sectoral working groups in areas like health and cultural cooperation, alongside formal institutions such as the NDB. Amongst the BRICS+

core agenda, there is and has been a persistent consensus on the need to balance the global order by reforming the fora of United Nations, International Monetary Fund, and World Bank to reflect the actual economic weight of emerging powers (BRICS Brasil, 2025a). Other core points of agreement seem to be a defense of "multilateral diplomacy" over U.S. primacy, a financial reform reducing global dependence on the US dollar, a development agenda, and multi-polar regionalism based on the rule of international law (Prashad, 2013, p. 13).

However, bloc's capacity to act as a unified policy-maker is frequently hindered by deep ideological and political inconsistencies. This is especially true when the actions of a member violate the institutionalized conceptions of human rights and/or international stability. South Africa proves a pivotal example of this friction. Gruzd and Von Treskow (2026) observe that, despite much Western pressure and criticism from domestic actors, Pretoria consistently uses its position in BRICS to provide diplomatic cover for Moscow, choosing to abstain from UN General Assembly resolutions condemning Russia's international violence since 2022. They point to a further consolidation of its positioning by signaling a military alliance with China and Russia through the Mosi II naval drills in 2023 (Gruzd and Von Treskow, 2026).

Values championed by each state, then, are pillars for political decisions of BRICS+ and define "what will win" in an arena where various projects are competing for relevance. That understanding is shared by Campbell (2004), who employs a prism of analysis referring to the widely accepted work of Richard W. Scott (2001) to explain that institutions can have three basic dimensions or pillars:

"The regulative pillar consists of legal, constitutional, and other rules that constrain and regularize behavior. The normative pillar involves principles that prescribe the goals of behavior and the appropriate ways to pursue them. The cultural-cognitive pillar entails the culturally shaped, taken-for-granted assumptions about reality and the frames through which it is perceived, understood, and given meaning." (Campbell, 2004, p. 36)

In that sense, giving due importance to the internal values of BRICS+ members matches Campbell's (2004) idea that institutional pillars like the cultural-cognitive and normative dimensions often precede and facilitate formal changes in governance structures. The states' many different "institutionalized rules of action and systems of meaning" change in an uneven manner, explaining the more incremental and slower pace that the process of institutional building and change, also known in this case as policy-making, can end up adopting (Campbell, 2004, p. 39).

As the path towards recognition of BRICS+ as a geopolitical coalition progresses, its continuity rests heavily on whether foreground discursive abilities of BRICS+ representatives can mobilize towards aligning these underlying values before they are even reflected in formal treaties.

Implications: Ideational Cohesion Within BRICS+?

The analysis presented in this paper carries several implications for the study of the BRICS grouping and its evolving role in global governance. First, it suggests that analytical approaches that interpret the grouping solely through economic cooperation or strategic balancing against Western institutions risk overlooking key aspects of its institutional development. As the bloc expands its agenda through processes of institutional and thematic densification, it increasingly operates as a political arena where member states negotiate priorities, norms, and collective initiatives. Understanding BRICS+ therefore requires closer attention to the ideational dynamics that shape these interactions and influence the direction of its institutional evolution.

Second, the findings highlight the structural tensions generated by the bloc's institutional design. Operating under a consensus-based decision-making model while simultaneously expanding its membership to states with highly diverse political systems and geopolitical orientations creates persistent challenges for collective action. As illustrated by moments of institutional strain, such as the divergent reactions of member states to international crises or shifts in domestic political leadership, BRICS+ remains highly sensitive to the ideological orientations of the governments that compose it. In this context, internal political changes within member states and intra-BRICS political developments can significantly reshape the bloc's priorities and affect the continuity of its cooperative initiatives.

These dynamics raise an important question regarding the long-term viability of BRICS+ as a geopolitical coalition: to what extent does the bloc require a set of minimally shared values to sustain deeper cooperation? While the grouping has historically maintained consensus around broad principles such as the reform of global governance institutions, the defense of multilateralism, and the promotion of a multipolar international order (Prashad, 2013), significant divergences remain regarding issues like political models, human rights norms, and attacks on international stability.

From an institutionalist perspective, these dynamics indicate that the sustainability of deeper cooperation within BRICS+ may, indeed, increasingly depend on the presence of minimally shared normative commitments among member states. As the bloc expands with ideological heterogeneity, common understandings regarding the principles guiding collective action may become an important condition for maintaining effective consensus-based coordination. Future research may benefit from examining whether the absence or presence of such common understandings influences the bloc's ability to translate political dialogue into concrete policy initiatives.

This discussion underscores the importance of addressing the values that underpin cooperation within the bloc. As institutionalist debates - like Campbell (2004) - suggest, normative and cultural-cognitive dimensions often precede and shape formal institutional developments. Regarding BRICS+, greater clarity upon the principles guiding its collective action could help reduce internal uncertainty, facilitate coordination among members, and strengthen the bloc's external legitimacy in the international arena. Ignoring the role of

values risks obscuring one of the central dynamics shaping the bloc's current trajectory.

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